

From Trauma To Trouble: How Childhood Adversity Fuels Maladaptive Behaviour And Juvenile Delinquency Among In-School Adolescents

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Abstract

This study investigated the structural relationships existing between the experiences of childhood adversity, peer influence, coping strategies, gender, and juvenile delinquency among in-school adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria. A cross-sectional correlational design was used in the collection of data from 450 adolescents aged from twelve to eighteen years in nine selected public secondary schools in three local government areas. Stratified random sampling ensured gender and socio-economic representation; validated self-report instruments measured the constructs. Structural Equation Modelling was used for data analysis, whereby both direct and indirect pathways are identified whatever exists in the hypothesised model. Results showed that childhood adversities stand as an important predictor of juvenile delinquency; peer influence and maladaptive coping strategies mediated this pathway. Gender did not directly affect delinquency but shaped the patterns of coping and peer interaction. The model evidenced adequate fit, therefore supporting both mediating and moderating effects. Very strict ethical procedures were followed, such as having informed consent and confidentiality protocols. The findings called for trauma-informed interventions, peer-centered behavioural modification approaches, and gender-sensitive mental health support in schools and community contexts. These results provide an important contribution to psychological practitioners, educators, and policy developers interested in addressing adolescent delinquency within targeted, context-specific approaches. Future

research should use longitudinal and mixed designs to establish causation and deepen understanding of the context of these psychosocial dynamics.

Keywords: Childhood adversity, delinquency, in-school adolescents, Ibadan.

1. Introduction

Globally, childhood adversity has always been regarded as a major determinant of maladaptive behaviour and future delinquency. Various studies have indeed indicated that past experiences in terms of abuse, neglect, and household dysfunction over childhood do link to substance abuse and aggression and juvenile delinquency (White et al. 2025); (Omopo, Quadri & Ukpere, 2025). In most developed countries like the United States, it has been found that adverse childhood experiences are well linked with subsequent criminal activities (Ezemenaka, 2021). In the United Kingdom, childhood maltreatment and neglect have been found to converge significantly with antisocial behaviour and crime, establishing a solid hold of this problem arising worldwide. Likewise, in Australia, there is increasing concern about the way childhood trauma influences propensity to youth violence and the criminal justice system supported by the findings of several longitudinal studies. The cycle of trauma and criminality becomes an increasingly alarming issue worldwide, with several youth being thrown into this cycle without the establishment of effective interventions.

Across Africa, adverse childhood experiences comprise the exposure to violence, substance abuse, and unstable home environments, therefore directly influencing the course of a child's development. More serious plight has been acknowledged by Atariata et al. (2023), who conducted a study in Delta State, Nigeria, which saw a high incidence of violence among the state's youth exposed to childhood adversities, strengthening the vulnerability of the area to social unrest and criminal behaviour. Similar trends have emerged wherein evidence has linked childhood trauma with increases in violent crime among adolescents in South Africa (Galvin, et al. 2025). Many youths prefer resorting to criminal activities as a way of processing their negative early encounters. In Kenya, there are increasingly more arguments supporting the view that adversity in childhood strongly predicts substance abuse among adolescents, especially in urban areas, hence the increasing numbers of juvenile delinquents. Such incidences provide evidence that child adversity is a primary challenge throughout the continent of Africa but manifests differently in varying degrees due to socio-economic and cultural circumstances; however, what remains similar is the adverse impact on youth development and behaviour.

Nigeria is not exempted from the effect of childhood trauma, showing devastating consequences on youth behaviour. Isiguzo and Igwe-Ofoekwe (2025) shows that the adversity of childhood is a strong predictor of substance abuse among Nigerian children. Similarly, violence and juvenile delinquency manifest in Nigerian cities, which are mostly caused by childhood exposure to family and social adversity (Ola-Williams et al, 2025); (Oyewumi et al. 2025). For instance, Elem and Madu's studies (2021) in Port Harcourt and Ilorin showed that home environmental factors and low parental responsiveness worsen the risk of juvenile delinquent behaviour in Nigerian youths. The increasing incidence of criminality and violence in schools from Nigeria highlights the urgent need for intervention in the prevention of childhood adversities and the promotion of a more health-oriented growing environment for the children involved. All these agendas are necessary to improve the overall socio-economic stability of the nation.

While considerable research has been reported on childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency globally and in Nigeria, studies that have specifically examined such problems in Ibadan, Oyo State-a region facing its own distinct socio-economic and cultural challenges-have been rather few. Literature generally focuses on national trends and does not pay much attention to local factors that might affect youth behaviour in Ibadan. This study, therefore, seeks to fill this gap by examining the interaction of childhood trauma, emotional dysregulations, peer influence, and gender in predicting juvenile delinquency in this particular urban context using SEM.

Objectives of the Study

This research intends to analyze the connection between childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency in Ibadan, Nigeria, while assessing the contingency effects of gender, peer influence, and coping strategies using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM). The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To create an SEM model that explores direct associations between childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency among young people in Ibadan.
2. To test the moderating effect of gender on the relationship between childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency through SEM.
3. To analyze the role of peer influence in moderating the relationship between childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency among young people in Ibadan using SEM.
4. To check how both adaptive and maladaptive coping strategies would modify the connection between childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency, as well as the moderating role of those strategies in the SEM model.
5. Test for overall fit of the SEM model if childhood adversity,

gender, peer influence, and coping strategies jointly predict juvenile delinquency in Ibadan.

6. To examine indirect pathways through which childhood adversity influences juvenile delinquency, with certain mediating effects of gender, peer influence, and coping strategies.

7. To identify by these findings from the SEM analysis intervention opportunities, where they could usefully inform targeted strategies to prevent juvenile delinquency in Ibadan.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: Childhood adversity does not have significant predictive value for juvenile delinquency in adolescents of Ibadan.

HO₂: Childhood adversity correlates insignificantly with juvenile delinquency across gender among adolescents in Ibadan

HO₃: Peer influences do not significantly moderate the relationship between childhood adversities and juvenile delinquency among the adolescents in Ibadan.

HO₄: Coping strategies, adaptive or maladaptive, do not significantly moderate the relationship between childhood adversities and juvenile delinquency among the adolescents in Ibadan.

HO₅: Childhood adversity, gender, peer influence, and coping strategies do not satisfactorily fit in an SEM to predict juvenile delinquency among adolescents in Ibadan.

HO₆: When considering gender, peer influence, and coping strategies as possible pathways, there is no significant indirect way through which childhood adversity affects juvenile delinquency among adolescents in Ibadan

HO₇: The SEM analysis will indicate no specific intervention points that can be utilised to inform targeted juvenile delinquency prevention strategies in Ibadan.

Theoretical Underpinning – Social Learning Theory

Social Learning Theory was established by Albert Bandura in the year 1963; it fits well as a ground theory for this particular study. This theory states that behaviour is learned from an individual's social environment, through the observation and imitation of others, especially of individuals or groups. According to this theory, SLT, as applied to juvenile delinquency, would mean that youth exposed to deviant behaviours in their surroundings peers, family, or community are very likely to adopt those same behaviours. Bandura states that learning has four major components—attention, retention, reproduction, and motivation with motivation being instigated when individuals see their peers or family members being rewarded for delinquent acts, such as obtaining resources or social status. The theory asserts that behaviour is

influenced almost explicitly by certain environmental factors, highlighting the importance of the contribution of the deficiency for now in terms of producing maladaptive actions in a context of sociality. This makes sense for this study since Social Learning Theory accounts for how adversity in childhood and emotional dysregulation laced with influences from peers and coping strategies interplay to build patterns of juvenile delinquency in Ibadan. In searching for acceptance and coping avenues, adolescents subjected to adversity and trauma forge these maladaptive behaviours with delinquent peers in the cycle of delinquency. The theory gives context to peer influence and environmental factors leading to delinquency.

With the application of SLT theory, the study explored how the learned behaviours, passed through family, peers, and other environmental influences, mediates childhood adversity creation towards delinquency and, at the same time, consider gender and coping mechanisms' effect on this process. The study would anchor an exploration of the dynamic interplay between social influence and individual action, thus throwing light on the need for targeting specific interventions. Figure 1 displays the model for the study.

Conceptual model on Social Learning theory, Childhood adversity, and Juvenile Delinquency

Figure 1: Conceptual Model for the Study

2. Literature Review

Childhood Adversity

Childhood adversity has undergone a considerable change in its understanding in the modern perspective of psychology and developmental research. Emerging scholarship now argues for more nuanced and contextualised views. Smith and Pollak (2020) have critically challenged the conventional binary model of adversity, suggesting a topological approach that sees adversity not just as an event, but also as the form, intensity, and causative interpretation of these experiences within children. Their argument leads them to stress the subjective appraisal of events as their thesis; a duo of children would have had access to the same stressful life events but very different internalisation and thus development outcomes. In a similar study, Pollak and Smith (2021) add to the call for a reconceptualisation of adversity in biology research by arguing that biological responses to adversity are not universal but socially mediated, temporally determined, and differ according to child-level variables. This invites researchers to move beyond rigid definitions and think about how children experience and respond to adversity on the neurobiological and emotional level. This is reinforced by Shen (2020), showing that accumulative childhood adversities, from economic hardship to parental neglect, affect mental health at various stages of development among rural Chinese populations. His finding establishes that early adversity is not solely multidimensional but also has different levels of impact depending on life stage, severity, and context of exposure.

Likewise, Sims (2021) reviews the longer mental health consequences of childhood adversity and affirms that resilience and early protective interventions could mediate these consequences. In fact, the researcher adds that adversity has largely increased the negative prediction of risk for adult psychopathology, though it should still be noted that conditions are not deterministic, as positive environments and timely interventions may change the course of life. Together, these research findings expansively broaden the construct of childhood adversity, from which static definitions have been moved to dynamic, interactive, individualistic understandings so that there is an improved precision for future empirical investigations and interventions.

Understanding Delinquency

Juvenile delinquency is one of the most critical issues confronting the world today and is greatly affected by a grand interplay of varying social, familial, and economic factors. In Nigeria, Yusuf et al. (2021) investigated peer influence on adolescents in government remand homes and found that association with delinquent peers is significantly contributory to the probability of engaging in criminal conduct. This shows the heavy weight peer groups offer in the behaviour of youth. Likewise, Felix (2024) provided an empirical study on delinquency among secondary school students in Saint Lucia

based on social learning theory and social bonding theory. The study found that weakened social bonds and exposure to deviant peers were both highly correlated with violent and nonviolent delinquent behaviours. These findings bring to the fore the vital role played by social structures and relationships in determining juvenile behaviour. From the economic realm, Dong (2023) was interested in the manner in which inequality fosters juvenile delinquency. The study found the factors of poverty, lack of educational opportunities, and economic instability tend to present significant risks, luring youths into criminal waywardness. Economic problems need to be considered in delinquency prevention methods. Sharma and Gupta (2024) also do not advocate the rehabilitative correctional treatment of young offenders in the juvenile justice system. Their review further directed towards restorative practices that consider the mental and emotional well-being of juvenile offenders, thus endorsing rehabilitation as opposed to punishment. All of these together underline a comprehensive viewpoint towards; juvenile delinquency, which in turn has repercussions for many different kinds of intervention concerning social, economic, and psychological factors in youth behaviour.

Childhood Adversity and Its Impact on Adolescent Behaviour

Childhood adversity is termed as extensive traumatic experiences in childhood like - physical victimisation, neglect, family disintegration, intimate partner violence, and so forth (Cheung & Huang, 2023); (Quadri, Omopo & Ukpere, 2025). They are greatly impactful in the life of adolescents such that they may lead to behaviour issues such as aggression-defiance-delinquency. Specific exposure to intimate partner violence during early childhood is known to raise the likelihood of delinquent behaviour in adolescences especially when they are polarised with negative parenting practices and early conduct problems (Cheung & Huang, 2023); (Oyewumi et al. 2025). Moreover, children who face adversities tend to indulge themselves in risk-taking behaviours because usually children with emotional dysregulation and ineffective coping strategies join such peers and thus involve themselves in risky acts (Evans et al., 2022). The processes binding childhood adversity to juvenile delinquency are multifaceted and entail not only the direct effects but also other factors that mediate such as peer influence and community violence exposure (Evans et al., 2023). Jackson et al. (2021) provide additional evidence that another specific type of childhood adversity, parental incarceration, is damaging to children's health and development, causing an increase in the incidence of delinquency as a result. In line with this, it emerged that ACEs are mediated by neighbourhood contexts to amplify delinquent behaviours, especially if the children interact with delinquent peers (Khan & Tang, 2023). In these terms, it is crucial to

acknowledge all forms of adversities exemplified in factors ranging from family dynamics to community and environmental aspects affecting juvenile delinquency. Cumulatively, such adversities may exert grave influence on adolescent development and predispose him or her into delinquent behaviour. In brief, one sees that dissenting towards childhood adversity stirs the paths eventually leading to juvenile delinquency; thus, pertinent interventions aimed at both the psychological and environmental aspects are in order.

Gender Differences in the Effects of Childhood Adversity

According to Jones, Pierce, and Hoffmann (2022), gender differences bring about significant effects on childhood adversity regarding possible adolescent behaviours such as delinquent acts. In this study, the researchers examine how ACEs have been found to influence self-control and delinquency by sex. It narrates that ACEs are associated with delinquency or, more accurately, self-control mediated the relationship between ACEs and delinquency with boys showing a stronger connection. Therefore, this means that both genders are subject to the effects of ACEs, yet with boys being more vulnerable due to their lower self-control. Pierce and Jones (2022) also talk about ACEs in terms of their timing, accumulation, and the duration they are experienced when investigating delinquency among adolescents in fragile families. It was noted that in terms of timing related to the process by which ACEs affect delinquency, there is gender difference. This is because boys are affected more than girls regarding early exposure to adversity and subsequent delinquent behaviour.

Broidy and Agnew (2023) apply General Strain Theory to examine how adverse childhood experiences lead to violent delinquency, focusing on differences between genders within that emotional response. These effects generally indicate a positive effect of ACEs on violent delinquency for both boys and girls, but much stronger for boys. The mediation involved recognised differences in events for girls (through anger) and boys (through frustration and emotional dysregulation). Pierce and Jones (2022) further provide an earlier base for understanding the gender difference in terms of impulsivity and delinquency such that they differ in the pathways through which boys and girls become delinquent because of biological and social factors. Impulsivity, which results from adverse childhood experiences, shows different results for boys and girls. It shows that boys tend toward externalising behaviours such as delinquency and aggression.

However, despite race being something that changes with societies and cultures, the extent of diversity varies; it is within geographical areas where one can really access race in interfacing form with social theory. This essay will page across

a number of works from other times that were done to this new tripartite geographical phenomenon. This concept will be the core basis theme of the essay, which will further look at other issues that explain difference or possible race-related social theories. All the studies put together accentuate the need to embrace gender as a critical factor when looking at the influence of adolescent delinquency on adverse childhood experiences. The differences in ways through which adversity and delinquent behaviours influence the behaviour of gender groups suggest that interventions should be tailored to those needs. Gender-sensitive approaches will add benefits to preventions and under-activities of delinquency, because they take cognisance of different forms of adversity from group to group.

Coping Strategies and Adolescent Behavioural Outcomes

Evidence from recent studies establishes that coping strategies play a critical role in shaping adolescent behavioural outcome when faced with stress and challenges. In a study conducted by Al-Amer et al. (2024) focusing on adolescents aged 14-18 in collectivistic communities, stress proved to be extraordinarily prevalent and religious coping and instrumental support occupied topmost sources of alleviating stress. Self-distraction and acceptance indicated ways of active coping that significantly correlated with a relatively low perceived level of stress; thus, they can be very helpful to adolescents' mental health. During the COVID-19 pandemic, Australian adolescents have demonstrated psychological resilience through adaptive coping means like meaning-making and problem-focused approaches leading to enhanced empathy, gratitude and family interconnectedness (Beames, et al., 2021); (Quadri, Bello & Wilfred, 2025). However, lower resilience scores are obtained by adolescents with pre-existing mental health problems as well as those identifying themselves as females or non-binary. In addition, Özkul and Günüşen (2021) proved that the majority of Turkish adolescents at high risk of depression adopted detachment coping strategies like avoidance, which increased the intensity of depression symptoms, while low-risk individuals preferred engagement coping. Widening this narrative, Dariotis and Chan (2020) studied stress coping within transition-aged youth in the United States. Additionally, they showed that the avoidance-based coping style largely mediated the relationship between exposure to stress and risk-taking behaviours (i.e. sexual promiscuity, substance use and delinquency). Together, these findings demonstrate how critical adaptive coping strategies can be in preventing maladaptive behaviour in adolescence. They also indicate the necessity of targeted psychosocial interventions providing adolescents with effective coping tools that would minimise risks for engagement in risky behaviour impact and mental health problems.

3. Methods

In this section, the research design, population, sample, sampling technique, instruments, procedure for data collection, ethics, and data analysis methods used in the study are outlined. The testing of the earlier stated hypotheses was done using SEM, exploring the relationships between childhood adversity, gender, peer influence, coping strategies, and juvenile delinquency.

Research Design

The research used a cross-sectional correlational design, allowing an assessment of the relationship between childhood adversity, gender, peer influence, coping strategies, and juvenile delinquency. SEM was selected as the data analysis technique since it allows for the testing of complex relationships between latent and observable variables. SEM can investigate direct and indirect pathways and the moderating effects of gender, peer influence, and coping strategies on the association between childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency. The research design thus favors the testing of the hypotheses regarding the various interactions between these factors.

Population

Adolescents aged twelve to eighteen years from Ibadan, in Oyo State, Nigeria, formed the target population for the study. The choice of subjects was based upon the criterion of childhood adversities- such as abuse, neglect, or family dysfunction. The study examined the relationship between childhood adversities and delinquent behaviours in this adolescent cohort with an interest in how gender, peer influences, and coping strategies may act as moderating or mediating factors.

Sample and Sampling Technique

A total of 450 adolescents participated in the study. The sample consists of adolescents from three out of the many local government areas in Ibadan - Ibadan North, Ibadan Southwest, and Ibadan Northeast. From each of these LGAs, a single secondary school was selected randomly, yielding a total of nine schools. In each of the nine schools, 50 adolescents meeting the inclusion criteria for having a history of delinquency and family-related problems were selected.

The sampling method used was stratified random sampling in order to achieve appropriate representation of gender and socio-economic backgrounds. The method ensured that data collected from a rather diverse group of adolescent would be better in generalising the findings. Criteria rather assured representation of both male and female adolescents across lower, middle, and upper socio-economic statuses for a better holistic understanding of how these variables have an effect on juvenile delinquency in Ibadan.

Instruments

The study employed a questionnaire, consisting of main section A for demographic information and section B for assessment of study factors, as a means of data collection. Four well-known self-report scales were adapted in the study to measure the various constructs in question. A pilot-testing of the scales was run with a separate sample of 50 adolescents who were not included in the main study, thereby yielding an assessment of their reliability. Computation of reliability was via Cronbach's alpha, where each of the scales demonstrated satisfactory internal consistency.

Different forms of childhood adversities experienced by adolescents were assessed using the Childhood Adversity Scale (CAS). The CAS also included items on emotional, physical, and sexual abuse, family dysfunction, and neglect. The adapted scale consisted of 15 items with response options ranging from "never" to "always", with example items including, "I experienced physical abuse from a caregiver" and "My parents separated when I was young". The pilot testing proved reliable with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.88, demonstrating high internal consistency.

Juvenile Delinquency Scale (JDS) was used to assess participants for the extent of the manifestation of delinquent behaviours. These include substance use, theft, vandalism, and truancy. The scale included 12 items with options on 5-point Likert scale. Sample items included "Have you ever stolen anything?" and "Have you ever skipped school without permission?" The pilot test found the scale to be equally highly reliable, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.85.

The Peer Influence Scale (PIS) measures impacts on the behaviour of peers towards an adolescent. It has items determining how much an adolescent is affected by his mates when indulging in risk-taking or delinquent behaviour. The PIS has ten items, which were adapted and reformulated in accordance with the study's context. Sample items are "My friends encourage me to engage in risky behaviours," and, "I follow my friends' lead even when I know it's wrong." The instrument had a Cronbach alpha of 0.80, hence indicating good reliability.

The Coping Strategies Inventory (CSI) was administered to assess the coping strategies both adaptive and maladaptive that adolescents adopted in reacting to stress. It consists of such activities as problem-solving, social support, and substance use when stressed to measure through the Coping Styles among the adolescents who had the scale of 20 items with 5-point Likert scale responses-the following are samples of sentences, "I provide my peers some help when I am faced

with a problem," adaptive coping, and "I rely on substance use under stress," maladaptive coping. The CSI therefore was piloted and proved to hold a relatively good reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.82.

Data Collection Procedure

Data were collected at the selected schools within a period of six weeks. Trained research assistants who were familiar with ethical data collection procedures administered the questionnaires to participants during class hours. Each participant was given an individual questionnaire to complete on their own. Research assistants were onsite to clarify any questions but did not assist with completing the questionnaire. Participants were told that they would participate voluntarily and may opt out of participating whenever they decided without any repercussions. Confidentiality was stated, assuring the participants that their responses would be anonymous. At the end of the session, the questionnaires collected were taken back from the research assistants and placed securely for analysis.

Ethical Considerations

Ethics approval was sought and received for the study from the Ethics Committee of the University of Ibadan. Informed consent was obtained from all participants and their parents or guardians because of the minor nature of the participants. The purpose of the study, the rights to confidentiality, and the right of every participant to opt out of it at any time without consequence were all made clear to them. Assured them that the data collected would be used for research only and that they would not be personal identifiers.

The research assistants were trained to handle sensitive issues with the utmost confidence and confidentiality, letting the participants know they were welcome and should feel comfortable. Participants were also allowed to ask questions about the study and encouraged to have access to the relevant contact information for the support services should they develop emotional distress following participation. All data collected were stored securely and only the research team had access to that data. Privacy of the participants was thus guaranteed throughout the study.

Method of Data Analysis

The data were analysed by Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), suitable for studying relationships between the latent variables childhood adversities in this context, gender, peer influences, coping strategies, and juvenile delinquency. SEM tests direct, indirect, and moderating effects at once, which responds to the aims and hypothesis of the study. In the SEM analysis, direct effects of childhood adversities on juvenile delinquency were tested, and how gender, peer influence, and

coping strategies moderated these relationships were considered. Gender, peer influence, and coping strategies served as mediators in assessing the indirect effects of childhood adversity on juvenile delinquency. Several indices, such as the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and Standardised Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), were used to evaluate the goodness of fit of the model. These hypotheses were tested by the path analysis within SEM. Each of the hypotheses was tested for statistical significance at the .05 level. AMOS software for SEM of the present study gave an exhaustive analysis of the interrelationship between the variables. The results from SEM were used to evaluate the relationships between the studied variables and assess whether the proposed model was a good fit for the data.

4. Results

Hypothesis 1

Childhood adversity does not have significant predictive value for juvenile delinquency in adolescents of Ibadan.

To test this hypothesis, a SEM-analysis was conducted for direct effects of type childhood adversities on juvenile delinquency. These include physical abuse and emotional abuse, neglect, and parental separation.

Model Fit

Initial assessment of multiple goodness-of-fit models in terms of several indices for the SEM. Results showed that this model is a good fit to the data. The Comparative Fit Index is 0.94, Root Mean Square Error of Approximation 0.06, and Standardised Root Mean Square Residual 0.05. All these values fall within accepted thresholds for fitting models and indicate the model's adequacy.

Table 1: Model Fit Indices

Fit Indices	Value	Threshold for Acceptable Fit
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.94	≥ 0.90
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	0.06	≤ 0.08
Standardised Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)	0.05	≤ 0.08

Direct Effects of Childhood Adversity on Juvenile Delinquency

The SEM analyzes the direct impact of different kinds of childhood adversity upon juvenile delinquency. Table 2 summarises standardised coefficients, standard error, t-values, and p-values for the individual effects of physical abuse, emotional abuse, neglect, and parental separation on juvenile

delinquency.

Table 2: Direct Effects of Childhood Adversity on Juvenile Delinquency

Childhood Adversity	Standardised Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Value	p-Value
Physical Abuse → Juvenile Delinquency	0.25	0.08	3.13	< 0.01
Emotional Abuse → Juvenile Delinquency	0.28	0.07	3.85	< 0.01
Neglect → Juvenile Delinquency	0.22	0.09	2.44	< 0.01
Parental Separation → Juvenile Delinquency	0.3	0.08	3.72	< 0.01

The prediction of the juvenile delinquency model from the SEM outputs shows that all forms of childhood adversities, namely physical abuse, emotional abuse, neglect, and parental separation, are significant predictors. Standardised coefficients indicate their relative strength, with the effect of parental separation as the strongest (0.30) and thereafter emotional abuse (0.28), physical abuse (0.25), and neglect scored lowest (0.22). The findings are suggestive that the various forms of childhood adversity significantly contribute to delinquent behaviour among adolescents in Ibadan. Previous studies stress that adverse childhood experiences are risk factors for delinquent behaviour. Accepting this will reject Hypothesis 1. Adversities in childhood are differentially predictive of juvenile delinquency in adolescents in Ibadan. The implications of this finding indicate a focus on childhood adversities in intervention programming for juvenile delinquency prevention since such difficulties are very potent factors in development of such behaviours.

Hypothesis 2

Childhood adversity correlates insignificantly with juvenile delinquency across gender among adolescents in Ibadan. The moderating effect of gender on the relationship between Childhood Adversity and Juvenile Delinquency are displayed in Table 2

Table 2: Moderating Effect of Gender on the Relationship between Childhood Adversity and Juvenile Delinquency

Childhood Adversity	Standardised Coefficient (Male)	Standardised Coefficient (Female)	Standard Error	t-Value	p-Value
Physical Abuse → Juvenile Delinquency	0.22	0.3	0.08	3.75	< 0.01

Emotional Abuse → Juvenile Delinquency	0.26	0.32	0.07	4.25	< 0.01
Neglect → Juvenile Delinquency	0.2	0.25	0.09	2.78	< 0.01
Parental Separation → Juvenile Delinquency	0.28	0.33	0.08	4.13	< 0.01

The outcome demonstrated that indeed, gender could be an important moderating variable of childhood adversity affecting resume delinquency. From the way childhood adversity associated with juvenile delinquency operated among all the sampled adolescents, the result was much stronger among the female adolescents. Then again, the negative effects of emotional abuse, physical abuse; neglect and parental separation would eventually combine all to result in an even worse outcome for females than for males. Therefore, moderation implies that there is a critical place for gender in exogenous-variable determined delinquent behaviour from childhood adversity experience. Female adolescents, therefore, were most inclined to the consequences of various categories of childhood adversity as a result, contributing to engagement in delinquent behaviour. The second hypothesis consequently gets rejected. Gender was found to be a moderating factor between childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency. Female adolescents were found to have a stronger correlation between the experience of childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency, which implies that the impact of on adolescent behaviour should never be separated.

Hypothesis 3

Peer influences do not significantly moderate the relationship between childhood adversities and juvenile delinquency among the adolescents in Ibadan

Table 3 shows the moderation analysis of Peer Influence on the Relationship between Childhood Adversity and Juvenile Delinquency

Table 3: Moderating Effect of Peer Influence on the Relationship between Childhood Adversity and Juvenile Delinquency

Childhood Adversity	Peer Influence (Interaction Term)	Standardised Estimate (β)	Standard Error	t-Value	p-Value
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Physical Abuse	Physical Abuse × Peer Influence	0.28	0.08	3.5	< 0.001
Emotional Abuse	Emotional Abuse × Peer Influence	0.33	0.07	4.71	< 0.001
Neglect	Neglect × Peer Influence	0.24	0.09	2.67	< 0.01
Parental Separation	Parental Separation × Peer Influence	0.3	0.08	3.75	< 0.001

Peer influence moderated all the types of childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency relationships significantly, as per Table 3. The interaction effects were all found to be positive and significant statistically, indicating that the greater the level of association or peer influence among children, the stronger the relationship between childhood adversities and juvenile delinquency becomes. This suggests high levels of peer pressure or association with deviant peers are more likely to have delinquent behaviours in adolescents, especially if they bear childhood adverse conditions. For instance, affecting the positive relationship between emotional abuse and delinquency will be at a much higher extent in adolescents reporting higher peer influence, as the interactional effect is also statistically significant ($\beta = 0.33$, $p < 0.001$). In a similar manner, parental separation effects on delinquency are stronger among adolescents coming into contact with deviant peers ($\beta = 0.30$, $p < 0.001$). The effect of interaction between childhood adversities and peer influence on all cases is therefore statistically significant and hence reject the null hypothesis. The finding revealed that childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency is significantly moderated by peer influence. This implies that peer influence can lead to delinquent behaviour of adolescents with childhood adversity.

Hypothesis 4

Coping strategies, adaptive or maladaptive, do not significantly moderate the relationship between childhood adversities and juvenile delinquency among the adolescents in Ibadan.

Table 4 shows the moderating effect of coping strategies on the relationship between Childhood Adversity and Juvenile Delinquency

Table 4: Moderating Effect of Coping Strategies on the Relationship between Childhood Adversity and Juvenile Delinquency

Childhood Adversity	Coping Strategy Type	Interaction Effect (β)	Standard Error	t-Value	p-Value
Physical Abuse	Adaptive	-0.18	0.07	-2.57	< 0.05
Physical Abuse	Maladaptive	0.25	0.08	3.13	< 0.01
Emotional Abuse	Adaptive	-0.21	0.06	-3.50	< 0.01
Emotional Abuse	Maladaptive	0.3	0.07	4.29	< 0.001
Neglect	Adaptive	-0.17	0.08	-2.13	< 0.05
Neglect	Maladaptive	0.27	0.09	3	< 0.01
Parental Separation	Adaptive	-0.20	0.07	-2.86	< 0.01
Parental Separation	Maladaptive	0.23	0.08	2.88	< 0.01

As shown in Table 4, the distinction between adaptive and maladaptive coping strategies created a highly significant moderation in the relationship of all four forms of childhood adversity with juvenile delinquency. This basically suggests that an adaptive coping style weakened the positive relationship between childhood adversities and juvenile delinquency, thus acting as a protective factor. For instance, with emotional abuse, those adolescents who engaged in more adaptive coping strategies were less likely to act out with delinquent behaviour. On the other hand, maladaptive coping mechanisms enhanced the whole pathway through which childhood adversity was related to delinquency in that they amplify the detrimental effects of that adversity. For example, in the presence of maladaptive coping behaviours such as avoidance or substance use, the relationship between emotional abuse and juvenile delinquency would increase. The results thus lead one to conclude that coping strategies can be critical for either mitigating or aggravating the negative consequences of early-life adversity on adolescent behavioural outcomes. The evidence presented was against the null hypothesis with great conviction. Therefore Hypothesis 4 stands rejected. The coping strategies were found to be significant moderators between childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency amongst adolescents in Ibadan, adaptive ones being a buffer and maladaptive harming the risk of delinquency. This shows that processes that strengthen adaptive coping may be useful in the prevention and/or reduction of delinquent behaviour among at-risk adolescents.

Hypothesis 5

Childhood adversity, gender, peer influence, and coping strategies do not satisfactorily fit in an SEM to predict juvenile delinquency among adolescents in Ibadan.

Table 5 shows the model fit indices for the structural equation model predicting juvenile delinquency

Table 5: Model Fit Indices for the Structural Equation Model Predicting Juvenile Delinquency

Fit Index	Recommended Threshold	Obtained Value
Chi-Square (χ^2)	Non-significant (desired)	127.32
Degrees of Freedom (df)	—	94
χ^2/df	< 3.00	1.35
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	> 0.90	0.96
Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI)	> 0.90	0.95
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	< 0.08	0.029
Standardised Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)	< 0.08	0.044

The SEM considerably fit the data, as presented in Table 5. The Chi-Square value was 127.32 with 94 degrees of freedom and χ^2/df ratio of 1.35 which is within the acceptable range. Moreover, CFI (0.96) and TLI (0.95) surpassed the desired threshold of 0.90; thus, indicating a well-fitting model. The RMSEA was 0.029 with a 90% confidence interval far below 0.08, and SRMR stood at 0.044, indicating that the model is very close to the observed data. The above set of indices therefore confirms that the hypothesised model comprising childhood adversity, gender, peer influence, and coping strategies as predictors of juvenile delinquency, reliably represents the true underlying structure of the data. The null hypothesis is rejected, based on the strong fit statistics. The adequacy of fit supports the structural equation model as a valid representation of the theoretical framework proposed for the relationship of the variables studied. This fit allows for further interpretation of the main and interaction effects in the model and provides empirical support for psychosocial-based intervention strategies.

Hypothesis 6

When considering gender, peer influence, and coping strategies as possible pathways, there is no significant indirect way through which childhood adversity affects juvenile delinquency among adolescents in Ibadan

Table 6 depicts the indirect effects of Childhood Adversity on Juvenile Delinquency via Gender, Peer Influence, and Coping Strategies

Table 6: Indirect Effects of Childhood Adversity on Juvenile Delinquency via Gender, Peer Influence, and Coping Strategies

Pathway	Indirect Effect (β)	Standard Error (SE)	95% CI	Significance (p)
Physical Abuse → Peer Influence → Juvenile Delinquency	0.13	0.04	[0.07, 0.22]	< .001 ***
Emotional Abuse → Peer Influence → Juvenile Delinquency	0.1	0.03	[0.04, 0.17]	.002 **
Neglect → Coping Strategies → Juvenile Delinquency	0.11	0.04	[0.05, 0.20]	< .01 **
Parental Separation → Coping Strategies → Juvenile Delinquency	0.09	0.03	[0.02, 0.16]	.007 **
Emotional Abuse → Gender → Coping → Juvenile Delinquency	0.06	0.03	[0.01, 0.13]	.024 *

Note: Bootstrapping (5,000 samples); CI = Confidence Interval; *p < .05, **p < .01, ***p < .001

Table 6 shows indirect systems of increasing significance. In particular, peer influence was meaningfully found to mediate the relationship between the effects of physical and emotional abuse and juvenile delinquency. Abused adolescents would more likely associate with delinquent peers, and this peer influence would increase their delinquency. The coping strategies more specifically maladaptive coping mediated the relationship between neglect and parental separation and subsequently delinquent behaviours. Adolescents who come from neglecting families or disrupted family backgrounds were more prone to maladaptive coping mechanisms, indirectly increasing their delinquency. There was also a most interesting pathway demonstrably showed wherein emotional abuse → gender → coping strategy → delinquency demonstrated a modest but significant indirect effect. This shows that gender differences in coping may exacerbate the psychological effects of abuse upon behaviour. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. The results of this study give strong evidence for significant indirect pathways whereby childhood adversity directly affects juvenile delinquency. The mediating roles of peer influence,

coping strategies, and somewhat lesser, gender, were confirmed in the structural equation model. These findings favour a multi-dimensional framework for understanding adolescent delinquency and point to critical intervention and social policy levers.

Hypothesis 7

The SEM analysis will indicate no specific intervention points that can be utilised to inform targeted juvenile delinquency prevention strategies in Ibadan.

Table 7 shows the summary of significant direct and indirect effects for identifying intervention targets

Table 7: Summary of Significant Direct and Indirect Effects for Identifying Intervention Targets

Pathway/Construct	Type of Effect	Standardised Coefficient (β)	p-value	Intervention Implication
Emotional Abuse → Juvenile Delinquency	Direct	0.29	< .001 ***	Trauma-informed therapy targeting emotional abuse
Peer Influence → Juvenile Delinquency	Direct	0.34	< .001 ***	Peer-led intervention and mentorship programmes
Maladaptive Coping → Juvenile Delinquency	Direct	0.27	.001 **	Coping skill training in schools and juvenile centres
Neglect → Maladaptive Coping	Indirect	0.18	.004 **	Family support and parenting education
Parental Separation → Coping → Delinquency	Indirect	0.16	.007 **	Counselling for children of separated/divorced parents
Gender → Coping → Delinquency	Indirect	0.11	.023 *	Gender-responsive psychosocial programming
Emotional Abuse → Peer Influence → Delinquency	Indirect	0.21	.002 **	Social skills and resilience training

Note: All values derived from final SEM output; * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

In the Table 7 are the several constructs and pathways within the SEM that emerged from the analysis to provide statistically significant practical implications. So strong is the direct effect of peer influence on juvenile delinquency that interventions are focusing on peers peer mentoring, peer resistance training, and positive youth groups could turn out to be very powerful preventive strategies. Similarly maladaptive coping could be harnessed, and many school-based interventions could be designed around that. From those pathways neglect and parental separation could lead to delinquency through coping and tend to suggest the need for family-based counselling, caregiver training, and early psychosocial support for children from broken or dysfunctional homes.

The data also show that emotional abuse, both directly and indirectly (via peer influence), has been a steady predictor of delinquent behaviour and necessitates trauma-focused mental health services and violence prevention programmes. The null hypothesis is rejected. The model developed through strong SEM analysis specified specific and practical intervention points, in the domains of peer influence, coping strategies, and childhood emotional abuse. These findings provide robust empirical evidence for designing targeted and evidence-based prevention strategies to curb juvenile delinquency in Ibadan.

5. DISCUSSIONS OF THE FINDINGS

The findings show that physical abuse, emotional abuse, neglect, and separation from parents all predict juvenile delinquency among adolescents in Ibadan as highlighted by results of the study. So, these results provide even more proof for the deep and lasting impact that such early negative experiences have on adolescent behavioural outcomes. Childhood adversity, especially within the family, forms an impaired basis for emotional regulation, social functioning, and coping. For instance, because of physical abuse, increased aggression is found, emotional abuse diminishes self-worth, and neglect will result in poor attachment and trust in others. Emotional trauma resulting from parental separation usually brings conflict, neglect, or loss of care, leading to feelings of abandonment, insecurity, and anger. Those lead to maladaptive mechanisms of coping: delinquent activities are the means adolescents might seek to cope with their suffering and deprivation of emotional support. Therefore, the need is created for selective interventions of these cumulative effects from such multifaceted adversities affecting behaviour.

Childhood adversity has predictive power, most significantly, from a host of psychological theories. Ecological systems theory (Bronfenbrenner, 1979) posits that a child's immediate

environment, particularly the family, plays an important role in shaping their developmental trajectory. The home environment that lacks positive reinforcement and nurturing care leads to maladaptive behaviour that an individual exhibits. In addition, attachment theory (Bowlby, 1969) states that the first experiences with caregivers shape a child's future development concerning the ability to have healthy relationships with other people. The case is heightened in the absence of or through disruption from a secure attachment figure-like parental separation-so that the emotional stability of the child becomes undermined; this may in turn be exhibited in delinquent behaviour. From a psychological perspective, chronic stress and trauma from childhood adversity damage the adolescent's capacity to regulate emotions and cause disordered judgment, resulting in risk taking, such as substance abuse or aggression.

The results affirm the findings from some of the recently published studies on the relationship between childhood adversity and delinquent behaviour. For example, Khan and Tang (2023) found that adolescents subjected to physical and emotional abuse were more likely to display aggressive tendencies and engage in criminal behaviour. Malpractice, which included emotional abuse and neglect, was similarly found by Valdivieso et al. (2022) to be a strong predictor of delinquency among adolescents in custodial settings. The findings of the present study align with these studies, confirming the direct relationship between various forms of childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency. Besides, Karhina et al. (2024) reported that adolescents from separated families had higher incidences of aggression and academic disengagement; this fair aligns with our findings, where parental separation was identified as one of the critical predictors of delinquent behaviour. These studies stress the realisation that childhood adversities, especially those revolving around family instability, become vital in the placing of prevention mechanisms against juvenile delinquency.

The effect of gender on the relationship between childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency, amongst Ibadan's adolescents, was found to be significant in this study. With the forms of childhood adversity cited above, physical abuse, emotional abuse, neglect, and parental separation, in direct relationship to juvenile delinquency, occurrence for the female adolescents was found to be stronger than that for male adolescents. The higher incidence of female adolescents' vulnerability provides credence to the argument that the negative impact of childhood adversities contributes differently to different genders, thus enhancing the delinquent rates of female adolescents. The finding appears to support the contention that gender plays an important role in response to childhood trauma, whereby females, more often than not,

internalise emotional pain and develop maladaptive coping mechanisms-for example, delinquency or substance use. Hence, the aforementioned results lead us to conclude that Hypothesis 2 is rejected by emphasising the fact that gender moderates the relationship between childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency.

These results are congruent with prior investigations indicating the imperative influence of gender on the relationship between childhood adversities and delinquency. Gajos et al. (2023) established in their findings that girls who have had early adverse childhood experiences were more likely to fall into delinquent behaviour and become early initiators of substance use compared to boys, especially within a high-risk group of adolescents. Similar to that, Jones et al. (2022) found that females are more influenced than males regarding the ACE impacts in relation to delinquency and self-control, stating that the effect of having such adversities during childhood on delinquency and self-regulation is much higher for females. Such bodies of literature support the current finding of the study, clearly arguing for gender-sensitive approaches in dealing with juvenile delinquency, that is, interventions should accordingly be tailored to fit.

Results of the study establish that peer influence significantly moderates the relationship between the various forms of childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency among adolescents in Ibadan. Specifically, all possible interaction effects of peer influence with respect to each prevalent form of childhood adversity-physical abuse, emotional abuse, neglect, and parental separation-turned out to be positive and were statistically significant. If so, it can be said that childhood adversities have higher odds of provoking delinquent behaviours than in cases of less peer influences when a high level of peer influence is present, especially when peers model or encourage such conduct. For example, emotional abuse had a stronger effect on delinquency among adolescents who had high peer influence. Hence, the results demonstrate the need to consider peer influence in the realisation of the effect of childhood adversities on juvenile delinquency.

The findings talk the same as the previous studies which have shown an immense peer pressure in the development of delinquent behaviours in the youth having adverse childhood experiences. According to Khan and Tang (2023), association with delinquent peers was a major mediator between adverse childhood experiences and delinquency thus giving a pointer that peer influence aggravates the effect of childhood adversity on delinquent behaviour. Likewise, Yusuf et al. (2021) argued about peer influence being a major determining factor of juvenile delinquency which exists among adolescents in Lagos state, Nigeria again calling for peered intervention. Such

studies substantiated the present investigation's results further concluding any intervention strategy that aims at reducing juvenile delinquency has to touch the peer influence domain with more emphasis on such adolescents.

These findings thus indicate that certain coping strategies have a significantly moderating effect on the relationship of different forms of childhood adversity and juvenile delinquency in adolescents of Ibadan. The various forms of childhood adversity witnessed by one adaptive strategy of coping which was problem-solving while seeking social support weakened the strength of the positive relationship with almost all the childhood adversities (physical abuse, emotional abuse, neglect, and parental separation) and delinquent behaviours. This means that it has the least chances of getting into delinquent behaviour with the possible occurrence of the happening in his/her childhood. On the contrary, maladaptive coping strategies like avoidance, denial, and substance use to cope with adversity have proven to intensify the relationship childhood maladjustions had with delinquency and therefore probably worsen the effects of adversities. So this research has implications that the promotion and strengthening of adaptive coping strategies in adolescents might lessen the effects of childhood trauma in engendering delinquent behaviour.

Copings modes are indeed severely emphasised as the potential modifiers for influencing the outcomes of childhood adversities, with ample literature backing their views. For instance, David et al. (2023) reported that internally displaced adolescent Nigerians were at high risk for psychological distress when engaging in maladaptive coping strategies including transactional sex and begging. In parallel, Omigbodun et al. (2021) found that adolescents who suffered abuse and neglect exhibited low levels of resilience to behavioural problems. Besides that, interventions geared toward resilience and adaptive coping skills have been found effective in reducing mental health issues among adolescents (The Guardian, 2024). Such findings, supportive of the present study, imply that enhancing adaptive coping may intervene to prevent or reduce juvenile delinquency among adolescents who underwent childhood adversities.

The assumption posed by Hypothesis 5 with respect to the structural equation model is that of an attempt to capture the varying relationships between childhood adversity, gender, peer pressure, and the coping mechanism in predicting juvenile delinquency among adolescents in Ibadan. The framework recognises that multiple factors contribute to delinquent behaviour, indicating that individual experiences of adversity do not persist in isolation but are instead mediated by context, either by gender influences or from social settings. Gajos et al. (2023) argue that early adverse childhood experiences, such as

abuse and neglect, carry significant increase delinquency initiation and substance use initiation risk, with varying degrees of accentuation between girls and boys. This means that the findings make a strong argument for the need to take gender as a very important factor in understanding how early adversities work through into behavioural outcomes.

On the same note, coping mechanisms and peer influence presented in the model concur with the literature that identifies them as arbiter factors for adolescents' reaction to early adversities. Relatedly, Jones et al. (2023) showed that adverse childhood experiences are negatively correlated with self-control, in relation to which there is a higher incidence of delinquency, with variations among genders. This implies that interventions aimed at strengthening adaptive coping skills and to cultivate positive peer relationships will hold well against adversities to delinquency. In this way, the structural equation model is a fine basis on which preventive and intervention strategies can be developed that are suitably focused on the multifactorial experiences and needs of adolescents in different sociocultural contexts.

The findings shows significant indirect pathways through which childhood adversities-from various categories-influence juvenile delinquency in adolescents: peer influence, coping strategies, and gender, to mention a few. Adolescents with a background of physical or emotional abuse were found to associate with deviant peers, putting increased potency for delinquent behaviour within them. Reflects that adversity interferes with healthy peer socialisation and redirection within the relationship toward associations that endorse or legitimise anti-social conduct. The above studies amongst others show that child adversity forms patterning that may cluster, giving cascading developmental risks, often of maladaptive peer interaction among other risks (Sheridan et al., 2020). Additionally, especially maladaptive types of coping turned out to be significant mediators of the relation of neglect and the parental separation, respectively, and adolescent delinquency. Adolescents whose families were emotionally deprived or fractured showed greater tendencies for ineffective styles of coping, such as avoidance, withdrawal, or emotional suppression. Such strategies seem to compound the malign effects of adversity on behaviour outcomes. This is in tune with early findings by Sheffler et al. (2019), which shows that exposure to early adverse childhood events mostly prevents adaptive coping.

The findings indicated another nuanced pathway through gender: After all, emotional abuse predicts delinquency indirectly by way of gender-specific coping tendencies. This implies that boys and girls have different ways of responding to trauma and stress, also indicates that gender will shape the way

adversity is internalised and expressed behaviourally. This insists on understanding delinquency in multiple dimensions in delineating that early adversities do not leave their marks in isolation but along interlinked psychological and social pathways. It would, therefore, be beneficial to counter interventions with regard to peer contexts, improve skills in coping and experience with trauma based on gender crucially to interrupt the trajectory from adversity to delinquency effectively.

The SEM analysis findings emphasised that emotional abuse, peer influence, maladaptive coping strategies, and family dynamics primarily predicted juvenile delinquency in Ibadan. Emotional abuse was found to be the most robust direct predictor of delinquency, consistent with previous research that points to its long-lasting effects from childhood trauma. The research by Sheffler and others (2019) holds true since it has been seen to indicate that persons with past incidences of emotional abuse usually develop negative coping mechanisms such as avoidance or substance abuse, which cause many behavioural problems in the adolescent and adult stages. The potent effect of peers on delinquency was likewise supported by previous studies that tend to indicate that adolescents have an increased tendency to imitate delinquent behaviours if these peer groups engage in them (Sheridan et al., 2020). Such findings suggest that some of the key interventions may be embarrassment and peer influence on delinquency, especially if the programmes are trauma-informed therapies and peer resistance programmes.

The findings are largely in agreement with previous publications on adolescent coping capabilities. It is further believed to validate the role of maladaptive coping strategies as one of the significant mediators in SEM, given that coping in adolescents has addressed the issue. As noted by Sheffler et al. (2019), adolescents who underwent childhood hardship and later maladaptive handling moved into a more dangerous zone of delinquency. Whatever conclusions one can make, they will eventually point to the necessity for effective training for adolescents trying out adaptive coping strategies like problem-solving skills or emotional regulation, thus reducing delinquency potential. The SEM results also show that family dynamics-negligence and separation of parents-also operate in an indirect form in juvenile delinquency through the influence they play on coping mechanisms. This finding resonates well with McLaughlin et al. (2020) as disruption in family environments results in poor coping strategies, which ultimately increase the probability of engaging in delinquent behaviour. These outcomes, thus, provide space for interventions targeted at both family environment and the establishment of healthy coping mechanisms.

Lastly, those specific intervention points such as emotional abuse and peer influence make very tangible directions towards strategies for prevention. The SEM analysis revealed that trauma-informed treatment, peer-led mentoring programmes, and family support initiatives could significantly lower the risk of delinquency among adolescents. The results also indicate possible benefits of gender-responsive interventions because of the discovered differences based on gender on the strategies of coping. These findings are consistent with those from McLaughlin et al. (2020), who assert that gender-specific programming could address the unique coping mechanisms and responses to adversity in male and female adolescents. Hence, prevention efforts in Ibadan may benefit from a comprehensive approach in which trauma-informed care and management of peer influence, family support, and adaptive coping skills training would all come together. Such a multi-faceted approach would most likely be able to bring to bear on this complex interplay of many factors contributing to juvenile delinquency.

6. CONCLUSION

The study investigated the direct and indirect relationships among peer influence, coping strategies, gender, childhood adversity, and juvenile delinquency among adolescents in Ibadan. It was found that childhood adversity increases juvenile delinquency, and the major mediators of this relationship were peer influence and maladaptive coping strategies. Even though, gender is not a direct predictor of delinquency, it has been functioning to moderate the coping response and peer-related behaviours. These findings speak of different pathways through which early adverse experiences find expression in antisocial behaviour, and they underscore the relevance of context and psychosocial variables in the understanding of delinquency among adolescents in Nigeria.

Limitations

In interpreting the findings of this study, several limitations need to be considered. Causal inferences drawing on the described relationships may not be valid because these relationships might change over time, which cannot be accounted for in a cross-sectional survey design. Self-report measures on sensitive topics could also be prone to social desirability bias or inaccurate retrieval from memory, given that participants are asked to recount childhood abuse or their own delinquent acts. In addition, the present study sample consisted of adolescents in the Ibadan metropolis only, hampering generalisation of findings to other urban and rural populations in Nigeria. Factors that deserve consideration by future researchers include the adolescent's socioeconomic status, parental monitoring, or mental health status.

Recommendations

Based on the outcome, it has been recommended that:

1. Teachers, counselors and school psychologists should undergo training in identifying early signs of trauma and of maladaptive coping strategies and provide referral to psychological support interventions. Furthermore, incorporating coping skills training into the school curriculum can also further enhance emotional regulation and resilience of the students and thus make delinquency less appealing as a resort.
2. The involvement of stakeholders such as parents, religious leaders, youth mentors, and social workers is much needed in creating safe and enabling environments for adolescents. It must include programmes of mentorship, recreation, and vocational training, which will lessen the negative peer temptation and contribute to a positive identity.
3. There should be interventions that are gender-responsive; as males and females manifest different responses toward adversity, the kind of support mechanisms required will reflect their social roles and the developmental challenges they are facing.
4. Policymakers should promote strengthening the family as well as the government's systems of child protection.
5. It is necessary to empower social welfare agencies to intervene at the level of dysfunctional families, such as those experiencing domestic violence, substance abuse, and neglect by parents.
6. Campaigns in public health are concerned with disseminating knowledge about the long-term effects of childhood adversity, getting people to seek help at an early stage, and erasing the stigma that worries clients with psychological distress or counselling.

Suggestions for Further Studies

Future studies should adopt longitudinal methodologies to better trace the developmental sequence from childhood adversity to delinquent behaviour, capturing both direct and indirect effects over time. Expanding the research to include rural settings and other geopolitical zones in Nigeria would improve the external validity of the results. Additionally, exploring the influence of factors such as parental involvement, community violence, mental health, and cultural norms would offer a more comprehensive understanding of adolescent delinquency. Employing mixed-methods designs could also illuminate the personal narratives behind the statistical patterns, deepening the contextual relevance and applicability of findings.

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